

Reasons Left Behind Timeliness for uncertain conditions

Amitesh Kumar Singam ^{1*}, Muhammad Shahid ^{2*}

¹ IEEE student Member

² Department of Applied Signal Processing
amiteshsingam3@ieee.org

Abstract—It appears to be fatigue due to air quality which leads to necessity of brain chemistry recordings, i.e, shifting from present to timelines from actual Geo location of our earth happens for uncertain reasons but eventually it shifts to respective coordinate of actual Geo location when intersection of timelines happens with existing present.

Index Terms—Geo Statistics, Timelines, Brain chemistry, quantum chemistry

I. INTRODUCTION

Geo statistics within timelines are meant to analyze spatially correlated information and moreover concepts based on applied sciences are beneficiary to understand patterns and predicted values for unmeasured locations to quantify uncertainty based on weather forecast data since timelines are sometimes intersected to actual Geo location within our planet. Within applied sciences quantum chemistry plays vital role to understand spatial information when considering substances within timelines which eventually unfollows existing periodic table.

II. INDICES: AIR QUALITY INDEX

To Sustain within Timelines, we need to quantify Air quality due to drastically changing substances and this is were an find some beneficiary indices i.e, devices with Air quality indices to quantify air quality within existing timelines.

III. NECESSITY WITHIN BRAIN CHEMISTRY IS ESSENTIAL

when people confronting extreme climates, they unintentionally shifts into timelines, generally it happens with traveling people due to fatigue, release of a Spinel fluid results in drastical changes in brain chemistry and it takes some time to get adaptability of sustaining in timelines after 2nd phase i.e, release of brain fluid, people started getting used to respective timelines. Moreover in timelines, Quantum chemistry plays vital role in understanding release of spine fluid and as well as brain fluid release.

IV. QUANTUM CHEMISTRY : THEORY OF IONIC AND COVALENT BONDING

Generally, when electrons are transferred from one to another atom results in electrostatic attraction creating positive and negative ions and it is referred as ionic bonding and moreover in covalent bonding electrons are shared not transferred causing electro negativity i.e, tendency of an atom in

a molecule to attract itself. for instance in water element, H₂O, oxygen is shared between hydrogen. so basically atoms with different negativity i.e, with HCl(hydrogen chloride) and H₂O(water), if acid is a substance that donates the proton(H⁺) and base is a substance that accepts it then H₃O⁺(water molecule) becomes conjugate acid and Cl⁻(chloride) is referred as conjugate base. due to fatigue(happens very frequent in timelines and reason is air quality), this water molecule (H₃O⁺) can bring many changes in brain chemistry results in release of fluid.

V. CONCLUSION

With reference to schrodinger equation and relating it with quantum chemistry will eventually leads to understand that continuity of changes in brain chemistry due to fluid release will repair the Genetic information(DNA) of respective individual cited by quantum biology.